

Insect resistance

Some gall midge-resistant rice hybrids in northeast Thailand

Weerawooth Katanyukul, Wanit Yaklai, and Suchin Chantarasa-ard, Rice Entomology Branch, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand

Gall midges annually cause severe damage to rice in northeast Thailand, especially along the Mekong River. That damage, coupled with poor sandy soils, lowers rice yields. Insecticidal applications are economically impractical. Farmers object to currently available

varieties that are resistant to the gall midge (e.g., RD 4 and RD 9) because of their susceptibility to certain diseases and their unacceptable cooking qualities. Further investigation is needed to obtain desirable hybrids.

In 1975, 15 lines of rice hybrids were screened out of 60 lines. During the 1976 rainy season those 15 lines, with susceptible and resistant checks, were tested in a farmer's field at Piboonmangsaaharn, Ubonratchatani province, where annual gall-midge infestations are heavy.

Damage caused by the gall midge in

19 entries ranged from 0.8% for BR 1030-28-2 to 31.4% for RD 1, the susceptible variety (see table). Only two lines of the new hybrids were susceptible. However, many lines that showed little damage, produced very few panicles and consequently gave low yields. BR 1031-3-4-3 and BR 1031-7-5-4, from the cross BKN 6517-63-4-3/RD 9, showed a high level of gall midge resistance, a good plant type, a good number of panicles, and high yields. They also exhibited high resistance to brown spot. At heading stage, little to no brown spot infection was found on them although RD 9 and MN 62 M were heavily infected. These two lines are long grained, nonglutinous, and about 80 to 100 cm tall. They are taller than RD 4 and RD 9, which are grown in northeastern Thailand. Since local farmers like the tall plant type, BR 1031-3-4-3 and BR 1031-7-5-4 offer good promise as a substitute for RD 4 and RD 9 for gall midge resistance in northeast Thailand.

Infestation by the gall midge of rice end yield performance of gall midge-resistant hybrids at Piboonmangsaaharn, Ubonratchatani, Thailand.

Cultivar ^a	Damaged tillers (%)	Panicles (av. no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)
BR 1030-12-1	1.2	3.3	0.93
BR 1030-16-2	1.8	4.6	1.05
BR 1030-18-1	1.9	3.6	0.93
BR 1030-26-2	3.5	6.4	0.90
BR 1030-26-3	1.3	5.1	1.41
BR 1030-26-4	3.0	5.8	1.52
BR 1030-28-2	0.8	3.5	1.07
BR 1030-51-2	2.1	4.4	1.08
BR 1030-100-2	7.3	6.5	1.38
BR 1031-3-3-3	21.3	7.4	1.45
BR 1031-3-4-3	3.6	7.4	1.65
BR 1031-6-3-2	26.3	6.5	1.46
BR 1031-7-5-4	1.5	8.0	1.40
BR 1031-16-1-6	1.4	9.7	1.58
BR 1031-16-1-8	6.3	9.4	1.47
MN 62 M (R check)	3.6	4.9	2.05
RD 1 (S check)	31.4	8.5	1.09
RD 4 (R check)	6.8	8.5	1.53
RD 9 (R check)	3.7	9.3	1.37

^aBR 1030 = BKN 6625-109-1/RD 9; BR 1031 = BKN 6517-63-4-3/RD 9.

Some promising gall midge-resistant rice varieties at an Indian hot spot

U. K. Nanda, Jr., entomologist; and A. Roy, rice breeder, Regional Research Station, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Chiplima, Sambalpur (Orissa), India

The gall midge *Pachytiplosis oryzae* severely damages the main rice crop (May to November) in Sambalpur district of Orissa, India. Breeders since 1968 have incorporated into high yielding varieties a degree of resistance to the insect. Three varieties that attracted attention are RPW.6-17, RPW.6-13, and Sakti. Researchers in various centers have

Yield and silver shoot count of selected rice cultivars in a trial for gall-midge resistance. Orissa, India, 1973-75 wet seasons.

Designation	Parentage	Silver shoots (no./sq m)			Yield (t/ha)		
		1973	1974	1975	1973	1974	1975
ORS.461	Leung 152/IR8/2	7	22	21	4.47	1.97	3.04
RP.9-10-3-2-1-1	IR8/W.1251	9	7	1	3.76	1.33	2.56
RP.352-28-1-14	Eswarakora/IR8	9	3	3	1.42	2.20	2.40
ORS.261	Leung 152/IR8/2	10	11	7	2.34	3.01	2.16
RP.350-57-1-1	820862/820916	5	5		3.02	3.04	1.71
RP.352-25-2-1-1	IR8/Ptb 18//Eswarakora/IR8	2	9	7	1.09	0.81	1.50
13231	IR8/W.1263	96	20	40	2.59	0.32	1.38
RP.352-63-6-1-2	IR8/Ptb.18//Eswarakora/IR8	21	38	2	2.29	0.55	1.31
RP.351-9-1-1	820862/820851	12	14	4	0.93	0.78	1.12
2	Ptb 10/IR8	40	40	40	2.32	1.42	1.02
12754	IR8/W.1257	89	75	74	2.34	0.98	0.97
ORS.112	Leung 152/IR8/2	0	3	185	3.40	2.75	0.64
Jaya (susceptible check)		251	364	450	0.41	1.13	0.69